

Domain Expertise Assessment for Multi-DNN Agent Systems

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Abstract—Recently, multi-agent systems that facilitate knowledge sharing among Deep Neural Network (DNN) agents, have gained increasing attention. This paper explores the dynamics of multi-agent systems that support Teacher-Student DNN interactions, where knowledge is distilled from Teachers to Students. Within such systems, selecting the most compatible Teacher for a given task is far from trivial and can lead to low-quality decisions. Hence, the need arises for accurate domain knowledge evaluation. In that context, we propose including an OOD detection module in each DNN agent to enable effective agent expertise evaluation and precise identification of suitable Teachers. This setup allows Student agents to distill knowledge from the most knowledgeable Teachers within a specific domain, ensuring optimal system performance. To effectively utilize OOD detection in this context, we address key challenges such as determining the minimum data cardinality required to ensure optimal performance and reliable inferences of the OOD detectors.

Index Terms—Out-of-Distribution Detection, Multi-Agent Systems, Deep Neural Networks, Teacher-Student systems

I. INTRODUCTION

Multi-Deep Neural Network (DNN) agent systems support knowledge sharing among DNN agents, encouraging collaborative interactions [1]–[4]. Typically, the process of knowledge transfer among DNN agents involves the identification of one or more Teachers and several Student DNN agents/models. The selection of Teacher DNN agents is often based on the number of trainable parameters they possess [5]–[8], which is believed to correlate directly with the extent of knowledge embedded within a trained DNN model [9]. Several other methodologies have been developed to assess DNNs and their knowledge. Some approaches focus on identifying specific *knowledge points* within a DNN, aiming to quantify the knowledge contained [10], [11]. Other techniques measure DNN knowledge by analyzing the amount of information within its various layers, operating under the assumption that a greater information content indicates a higher level of encoded knowledge [12], [13]. While these methods are designed to assess both the quality

and quantity of knowledge [10], they fall short in multi-agent environments. In such settings, evaluating agents and selecting Teacher DNN agents requires considering multiple factors. These include the specific data domain, the machine learning tasks to be executed, and the overall objectives of the environment. This approach ensures that the selection and evaluation process aligns more closely with the complex dynamics and requirements of multi-agent systems. Student DNN agents learning from an unsuitable model can lead to persistent system errors that may even worsen over time, resulting in poor performance. Additionally, in scenarios where multiple DNN agents possess domain-specific knowledge for a particular task, choosing the right Teacher DNNs becomes increasingly complex. Consequently, there is a pressing need for a robust and efficient DNN agent evaluation specifically tailored for multi-agent systems.

Out-of-distribution (OOD) detection can be pivotal in cases of multi-DNN agent systems as it serves as a domain indicator, enabling the identification of the most appropriate Teacher DNN agent for specific data inputs. By implementing OOD detection algorithms, agents can gain insights into the training domains of potential Teacher agents. This approach simplifies the computational demands within the environment by using OOD detection as a domain indicator. It enhances the reliability of the inferences drawn and the overall performance and accuracy of the multi-agent system. This approach is especially beneficial in scenarios where Teacher agents do not provide access to their output or inference results but only share information about their training sets.

In this direction, an efficient evaluation method has been specifically developed for systems employing multiple DNN agents. This paper proposes the addition of an OOD detector module into each DNN agent within a multi-agent system to enable the assessment of each agent’s knowledge. The addition of an OOD detector module enables a systematic evaluation of DNN agents,

particularly in identifying which agent is best suited to become a Teacher for a specific task. Additionally, this study explores the minimal data required for the OOD detectors to provide reliable assessment inferences, thereby ensuring optimal system performance and reducing potential errors.

In summary, the primary contributions of this paper are outlined as follows:

- An efficient method for evaluating DNN agents within multi-agent systems, utilizing an OOD detector module embedded within each DNN agent is proposed. This approach provides a structured method for evaluating agent knowledge across various scenarios.
- We explore and determine the minimal data amount necessary for OOD detectors to produce reliable evaluations of the agents, ensuring that the system operates effectively with optimized data usage.

II. RELATED WORK

A. Teacher-Student learning in Multi-Agent Systems

Teacher-Student frameworks in DNN training are employed to strike a balance between training efficiency and performance [14], [15]. In this context, a well-trained, large DNN model is utilized as a Teacher, as demonstrated in [16]. The technique of distilling knowledge into a Student model has shown significant benefits [17]. Building on the findings from [17] and [16], subsequent studies have explored Teacher-Student DNN interactions to refine the process of efficient knowledge transfer, thereby enhancing Student DNNs’ training outcomes [8], [14], [18]–[21]. Although existing Teacher-Student DNN environments have significantly improved the training and inference capabilities of Student models through knowledge distillation, they have not yet fully explored the optimal selection of the most knowledgeable Teacher DNN to ideally train a Student DNN agent.

B. DNN Agent Knowledge Assessment

DNNs derive their performance from the knowledge encoded within their hidden layers during training. Accurate assessment of this knowledge is critical, particularly in complex multi-agent systems. Understanding how DNN knowledge is embedded within individual DNN agents and the broader context of unconstrained multi-DNN agent environments remains a significant challenge. In traditional approaches, DNN knowledge has been described as the output of a learned mapping $y = f(x_i, \theta)$ from input x_i to output vectors y_i [17]. Recently proposed DNN knowledge assessment methods attempt to leverage entropy to quantify knowledge encoded in an intermediate DNN layer [12], [13]. In other recent studies, quantifying the knowledge points encoded in DNN intermediate layers has been proposed

[10], [11]. The knowledge of an intermediate DNN layer can be defined as the set of knowledge points that are encoded by the neural activations/features of this layer.

Existing methods for assessing DNN knowledge have offered valuable insights, but they often fall short when applied to complex multi-DNN agent systems. Our research addresses this gap by introducing a knowledge assessment strategy tailored specifically for such environments. This method efficiently identifies the most knowledgeable Teacher agent, facilitating precise and effective knowledge transfer between agents. By minimizing computational demands, our approach enhances system performance and fosters trust among agents. This trust is crucial as it ensures the reliability of the agents’ inferences, thereby boosting the overall effectiveness of the multi-agent system.

C. Out Of Distribution Detection

OOD detection is used to classify data as either *in-distribution* (ID) or *out-of-distribution* (OOD), with OOD data points representing classes that the detector did not encounter during the training phase. In recent years, various OOD detection algorithms have been developed to determine outlying data points during DNN inference. OOD detection is an active research area for classification tasks, utilizing various techniques [22]–[26]. An obvious baseline OOD detection solution is to gather statistics on maximum softmax output probabilities for DNN predictions after the end of the DNN training process using a validation dataset. Examples that are classified accurately usually have higher maximum softmax probabilities compared to those that are misclassified, enabling their identification [22]. Subsequent improvements include using temperature scaling [27], the energy function [23], and the group-based softmax [28]. Additionally, there is research that goes beyond solely relying on ID data by incorporating actual [29] or synthetic [30] outliers during the training phase. To detect outlying data points, the softmax class prediction probability is compared against a threshold [31] for OOD detection purposes. A DNN classifier is trained to output confidence estimates for each input data point. They are then used to differentiate between ID and OOD examples [32]. An input is considered as being an OOD one if the confidence estimate is less than or equal to a decision threshold. In this context, Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) have been utilized [33].

Our approach involves incorporating OOD detection within each DNN agent in a multi-agent system, utilizing it as a training domain indicator. This offers valuable insights into the training data domains of each DNN agent, which are essential for accurately evaluating and choosing the most appropriate Teacher DNN agent.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

This paper asserts the importance of a comprehensive method for consistently evaluating DNN agents within multi-DNN agent systems. We propose the incorporation of OOD detection within each DNN agent, using it to indicate the training domain of the agent. To effectively utilize OOD detection in a multi-agent system, it is essential to determine the reliability of the detectors and thus, to establish the sufficient amount of testing data needed for OOD detectors to deliver reliable results.

Fig. 1. Integration of an Out-of-Distribution (OOD) Detection Module in each DNN agent to optimize evaluation in a multi-agent system. The selection of the Teacher agent is based on task-relevant In-Distribution (ID) data. The DNN agent possessing the most ID data is selected to function as a Teacher agent. We notate as $idx(\cdot)$ the function that returns the index of its argument and idx^* its output.

A. OOD detection in multi-DNN agent systems.

We suggest that equipping each agent with an OOD detection module is essential for evaluating the agent knowledge, achieving optimal performance, and generating reliable predictions throughout a multi-agent system. By implementing this approach, DNN agents can obtain information about the training domain of any potential Teacher agent. Our method not only reduces the computational complexity across the entire system but also enhances the reliability of the OOD detection inferences that are derived.

Deep learning models often struggle with real-world tasks when they encounter discrepancies between the training and testing data distributions. Typically, a DNN is trained on labeled data and later tested on unfamiliar test data during the inference phase, with both datasets assumed to share the same label space. However, when a DNN encounters data points during inference that are statistical outliers—possessing labels or probability distributions not present in the training data—it tends to make incorrect predictions. OOD detection algorithms

are designed to discern whether a test example originates from a distribution different from the training data or the same distribution [33]. In multi-agent systems, using OOD detection, the DNN agents can make decisions about the new data and whether they belong to their training data domain, with reduced computational complexity and heightened confidence. For classification tasks, when incoming data is accompanied by ground truth labels, the process of providing inferences and evaluating them becomes feasible for any DNN classifier agent component. However, coordinating all agents in a network environment to provide inferences for selecting the Teacher agent introduces significant complexity. Considering the challenges of label ambiguity or the lack of ground truth labels in incoming inference data, integrating an OOD detection module is essential. This module remains crucial even in situations where Teacher agents may not provide access to their outputs or inference results but only share information about their training sets. In such cases, the OOD detection module is still able to make reliable assessments about potential Teachers.

The OOD detection algorithm utilized is based on a Variational Auto-Encoder (VAE) using an OOD detection score, namely the Likelihood Regret (LR) [33]. It assists in making informed decisions about classifying new inference data as either ID or OOD, which is essential for determining whether the system can efficiently process the data for the intended task. The LR of an input data \mathbf{x} is defined as:

$$LR(\mathbf{x}) = L(\mathbf{x}; \theta^*, \hat{\tau}(\mathbf{x})) - L(\mathbf{x}; \theta^*, \phi^*), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{\tau}(\mathbf{x})$ is the optimal posterior distribution of the latent variable given the input data \mathbf{x} and θ^* the optimal decoder obtained from the training data set. The method utilizes a GAN to generate outlying data having low $P_{in}(\mathbf{x})$ probability values while a DNN classifier is trained and is forced to produce a small softmax value for the expected (correct) class when presented with GAN-generated outlying data during either the training or inference phase.

Let a multi-agent system comprise A agents, denoted as a_1, a_2, \dots, a_A , where each agent possesses an OOD detection module to evaluate its knowledge regarding a specific data domain, denoted as k_1, k_2, \dots, k_A . In our paper, we define “knowledge” k as the amount of ID data relevant to the incoming data for a specific task. We operate under the assumption that the agent with the most ID data related to the incoming data will possess the greatest capability to handle this data and execute the specific task, such as classification. This approach posits that a higher quantity of ID data enhances the DNN agent’s ability to perform accurately and effectively. Within the system, the knowledge k_i of an agent a_i can

be compared with that of another agent a_j , by examining the condition $k_i > k_j$ for $i \neq j$. This comparative assessment, presented in Figure 1 empowers the agents to make informed decisions about their ability to process new data efficiently. For instance, if the knowledge hierarchy for a specific task is $k_1 > k_2 > \dots > k_A$, it suggests that the agent a_1 is the most knowledgeable and capable. Consequently a_1 can serve as the Teacher for other DNN agents, guiding and enhancing the Student learning process.

B. Reliable Inference by OOD detection

Our research delves into the interactions between Teacher and Student DNN agents with the aim of identifying the most informed Teacher for specific tasks. This involves first examining the training domains of each agent to select the most appropriate one. When employing OOD detection to assess DNN agents, ensuring the reliability of inferences is paramount, as the entire system’s decisions depend on their accuracy. It is essential to select the most knowledgeable agents to impart domain-specific knowledge to Student agents and inaccurate OOD detection inferences can lead to suboptimal decisions. The OOD detection module plays a crucial role in identifying agents that have encountered data during training that align with the distribution of incoming data. To utilize OOD detection effectively, it is necessary to ascertain the amount of incoming data required for the OOD detectors to function properly. Once it is established that there is a sufficient volume of data to support dependable inferences, the DNN agent with the most ID data is selected to serve as a Teacher agent.

To determine the required sample size for reliable OOD detection inferences, individual testing of the OOD detector modules is conducted across various testing dataset cardinalities ranging from one data sample to two thousand data samples N . The mean value \bar{e} and the variance σ_e^2 of the evaluation metric values $e_i, i = 1, \dots, N$ for the total samples of testing evaluation metric is defined as:

$$\bar{e} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N e_i \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma_e^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (e_i - \bar{e})^2 \quad (3)$$

For each one of these cardinalities in the range $[1, \dots, 2000]$, the OOD detectors are also tested repeatedly ten times so that the mean value and the variation of the evaluation metric can safely be estimated.

The Shapiro–Wilk normality test [34] is used to determine whether a random sample, is drawn from a normal

Gaussian probability distribution, with true mean and variance, μ and σ^2 , respectively [35]. The true mean value (μ) is a population parameter that represents the average value of a variable across the entire population. To assess the normality of the evaluation metric values gathered by the OOD detectors, a Shapiro-Wilk normality test is employed on a random sample of 500 values. A confidence interval is a statistical range derived from a sample of data that is utilized to estimate a population parameter. The interval is accompanied by a confidence level, representing the degree of confidence in the interval containing the true population parameter. The most commonly used confidence intervals include those with confidence levels of 90%, 95%, and 99% with critical values (Z-scores) of 1.645, 1.96, and 2.576 respectively. The 95% confidence interval for the population mean \bar{X} can be expressed as:

$$95\% \text{ confidence interval} = \bar{X} \pm 1.96\sigma/\sqrt{n}. \quad (4)$$

To determine the sufficient number of testing samples required for reliable agent inferences, once it is confirmed that the evaluation metric values conform to a Gaussian curve, the sample mean \bar{e} , sample standard deviation σ_e^2 , and confidence intervals for the population mean are calculated. The minimum number of testing samples needed is determined based on the condition that the evaluation metric corresponding to that number equals the total sample size mean value \bar{e} , with a 95% confidence interval. In particular, the quantity of testing samples needed corresponds to the number of samples necessary for the network to attain an evaluation metric equivalent to:

$$\bar{e} + 1.96\sigma_e/\sqrt{N}. \quad (5)$$

This criterion ensures a sufficient level of confidence in the agent’s conclusions. Once it is ensured that there is a sufficient amount of data to make reliable inferences, OOD detectors can be utilized to evaluate the DNN agents in the multi-agent system.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we present the experimental results of our method for various datasets. Our objective is to determine the minimum number of samples needed for OOD detection modules to produce reliable results. By establishing this optimal sample size, we are then able to utilize the OOD modules to accurately assess the DNN agents and identify the most suitable Teachers within a multi-agent system.

To ascertain the necessary sample size for dependable outcomes, the OOD detector—the LR VAE [33]—is tested with varying numbers of test samples. The performance of the OOD detector is evaluated using

TABLE I
 OUT-OF-DISTRIBUTION (OOD) DETECTION EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS. THE METRIC USED TO EVALUATE THE PERFORMANCE OF THE OOD DETECTOR IS THE AUCROC. THE D_{in} IS THE IN-DISTRIBUTION DATASET, WHILE D_{out} IS THE OUT-OF-DISTRIBUTION DATASET. THE RESULTS PRESENTED ARE THE MEAN VALUES FROM TEN INDEPENDENT EXPERIMENTS.

Dataset and Test Samples	Number of Testing Samples	AUCROC	Standard Deviation
D_{in} : F-MNIST [36]- D_{out} : MNIST [37]	15	0.9533	0.0137
	50	0.9856	0.0294
	500	0.9237	0.0086
	1000	0.9556	0.0064
	1500	0.9680	0.0037
	2000	0.9582	0.00379
D_{in} : SVHN [38]- D_{out} : Cifar-10 [39]	15	0.7424	0.04696
	50	0.7139	0.0654
	500	0.7285	0.0031
	1000	0.7317	0.0080
	1500	0.7303	0.0078
	2000	0.7312	0.0042
D_{in} : Cifar-10 [39]- D_{out} : SVHN [38]	15	0.7984	0.02570
	50	0.7794	0.0333
	500	0.8294	0.0119
	1000	0.8359	0.0048
	1500	0.8364	0.0049
	2000	0.8295	0.00448
D_{in} :Cifar-100 [39]- D_{out} : SVHN [38]	15	0.7984	0.02570
	50	0.7076	0.0861
	500	0.8021	0.0147
	1000	0.8043	0.0074
	1500	0.8029	0.0030
	2000	0.8070	0.0051

the Area Under the Curve-Receiver Operating Characteristics (AUCROC) score, which offers a detailed measure of performance across different threshold levels [40]. Experiments were carried out using five well-known image classification datasets: Cifar 10 and 100 [39], MNIST [37], Fashion MNIST [36], and Street View Housing Numbers (SVHN) [38]. Cifar-10 and 100 consist of 50K training and 10K testing grayscale images equally distributed among 10 and 100 object classes respectively. Fashion MNIST and MNIST consists of 60K training and 10K testing grayscale images equally distributed among 10 object classes. Lastly, the SVHN dataset consists of 73257 training and 26032 testing images featuring labeled digits from street view numbers spread across 10 classes. Each experiment utilizes a pair of datasets: the first dataset, D_{in} , contains ID data samples, processed by our OOD detector, while the second, D_{out} , consists of OOD data samples. The key findings of our study are presented in Table I which shows the experimental results for multiple datasets and various testing data sample cardinalities in the range [1, ..., 2000].

Figure 2 presents a plot that examines the correlation between AUCROC scores and the number of samples used by the OOD detector during the inference procedure. The plot demonstrates that as the sample size increases, the variability in AUCROC scores decreases, resulting in a more stable range of values. Importantly, the AUCROC scores tend to stabilize beyond a cer-

tain number of testing samples, suggesting that further increases in sample size do not significantly enhance performance. This observation is crucial for identifying the minimum number of samples required to ensure reliable conclusions from the agents.

Fig. 2. Relationship between AUCROC scores and sample size for the dataset Fashion MNIST [36] as D_{in} and the MNIST [37] as D_{out} .

In Table II we present the estimations derived based on the methodology outlined in Section III. The values indicate the minimum sample size required by the OOD detectors for multiple D_{in} datasets. The results indicate that the OOD detectors can be considered reliable when providing inferences for 1% of the data cardinality they are trained on. This observation, consistent with the data presented in Figure 2, emphasizes that the OOD detector

can deliver accurate evaluations using only a small percentage of the data relative to what it was trained on, affirming its reliability and utility. Consequently, OOD detection is an effective and straightforward option for evaluating agents, tracking their domain expertise, and selecting the appropriate Teacher agent within a multi-agent environment.

TABLE II
MINIMUM NUMBER OF DATA REQUIRED TO ENSURE THE RELIABILITY OF THE OOD DETECTION MODULE FOR EACH TRAINING DATASET, D_{in} , AND THE PERCENTAGE IN RELATION TO THE TRAINING DATASET SIZE.

Dataset	Samples needed	Percentage of samples needed
F-MNIST [36]	586	0.98%
SVHN [38]	734	1.04%
Cifar-10 [39]	486	0.97%
Cifar-100 [39]	294	0.59%

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we proposed the inclusion of OOD detection modules within the DNN agents of a multi-agent system to ensure a reliable evaluation process, allowing the selection of the appropriate Teacher agent for knowledge distillation. This module enables DNN agents to discern whether new inference data should be classified as ID or OOD and assess if an agent is equipped to handle the data effectively for an impending task. The Teacher agent selection relies on the effectiveness of the OOD detectors and their capacity to correctly identify ID data, underscoring the importance of dependable OOD decisions. We have quantified the necessary data cardinality that OOD detectors require to accurately infer agent compatibility for incoming tasks. Our experimental findings reveal that only a minimal portion of the total data is required for the OOD detection module to make accurate inferences and effectively facilitate the Teacher selection process.

These results open up new prospects for enhancing multi-agent systems, especially through the strategic application of OOD detection to evaluate agents in DNN Teacher-Student interactions. This study sets the stage for further research into optimizing these interactions and extending their benefits across diverse multi-DNN agent settings and multi-modal tasks. Future investigations can explore how agents distill knowledge from multiple Teacher DNN models, enhancing the adaptability of DNN architectures in handling complex data inputs to improve operational efficiency in dynamic environments.

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